

Nauris Silkāns, "Development of fiber optical sensor system for structural health monitoring of infrastructure objects"

Version 0

Description

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed relating to the Academic career PhD (doctoral) grant, ID - 1011, project ID: 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/003.

Purpose of the DMP

The main purpose of this DMP is to ensure the orderly management of the results and data collected or generated within this project ensuring reliable and quality data retention, processing and analysis to facilitate the successful completion of the main goals of this project. As well as to guarantee long-term data preservation even beyond the life of this project to make it possible for all data to be accessible by researchers working in this or similar field.

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

Academic career PhD
(doctoral) grant

Researchers

Janis Braunfelds (orcid:0000-0001-8238-9328), Vjaceslavs Bobrovs (orcid:0000-0002-5156-5162), Nauris Silkans (orcid:0009-0004-4683-1026), Sandis Spolitis (orcid:0000-0002-0571-6409)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Nauris Silkāns, "Development of fiber optical sensor system for structural health monitoring of infrastructure objects"

Description:

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed relating to the Academic career PhD (doctoral) grant, ID - 1011, project ID: 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/003.

Purpose of the DMP

The main purpose of this DMP is to ensure the orderly management of the results and data collected or generated within this project ensuring reliable and quality data retention, processing and analysis to facilitate the successful completion of the main goals of this project. As well as to guarantee long-term data preservation even beyond the life of this project to make it possible for all data to be accessible by researchers working in this or similar field.

Researchers:

Janis Braunfelds (orcid:0000-0001-8238-9328)

Vjaceslavs Bobrovs (orcid:0000-0002-5156-5162)

Nauris Silkans (orcid:0009-0004-4683-1026)

Sandis Spolitis (orcid:0000-0002-0571-6409)

Organizations:

Riga Technical University

Contact: Nauris Silkāns

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission|EC

Grants: Academic career PhD (doctoral) grant

Data Management Plan | Nauris Silkāns, "Development of fiber optical sensor system for structural health monitoring of infrastructure objects" License: -
DOI: - 20/09/2024

Project: Academic career PhD (doctoral) grant

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

DMP

For the duration of this project, two main types of data will be generated: input data and output data.

Input data is the data that will be gathered from measurement equipment or simulation software, main format of input data will be tabular data (CSV and TSV). Output data of this project is processed and analyzed input data (CSV, TSV), Matlab scripts for data analysis or possible fiber optical system simulation schemes

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Accurate data collection is essential for maintaining the integrity, and quality of the project. The main purpose of data collection and generation is to gather relevant data in a well-established and systematic manner for further analysis to ensure that all generated data is freely available to anyone involved in the project, and to ensure good data management practices and quality control of the data, making data available for use in future studies and projects.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Event

- Programme source code
- Machine-readable text
- Experimental data
- Textual data
- Coded textual data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- txt
- pdf
- csv
- tiff
- png
- others

Matlab figure file (for generated graphs to ensure possibility for further high precision and quality measurements and analysis)

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

15

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

For this project, the re-use of existing data has been considered for obtaining reference data for research as well as for verification and validation of experimental setup and results. But as of this moment, there are no concrete plans to use existing data, if circumstances will change, this section will be changed accordingly.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data gathered for the duration of this project will be useful for other researchers in the field conducting studies related to fiber optical sensors and their utilization in structural health monitoring solutions to obtain possible references for research, to verify findings and results of the results. As well as to popularize this technological field and build a knowledge and experience base for further development of this type of technology.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

DC metadata elements

Element	Definition
Title	The name given to the resource.
Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
Description	An account of the content of the resource.
Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.
Relation	A reference to a related resource.
Coverage	The extent or scope of the content of the resource.
Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.
Publisher	The entity responsible for making the resource available.
Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.
Data	Data associated with an event in the cycle of the resource.
Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
Language	Language(s) of the intellectual content of the resource.

Image 1

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Data will be sorted in folders in the following hierarchy:

Topic (e.g. Experiment's name)

Date (Date the measurements were performed)

Folders describing other variables if necessary (e.g. Data channel for measurement equipment, if during one experiment, more than one data channel is being used)

Data folder with a tag to identify whether it contains raw experimental data or processed data.

The file name will include descriptive phrase, data channel (if necessary), and date, for example:

loading_test_CH1_26_06_24

The Data Log will be kept as well to track all activities related to gathered data, such as filename, date, format, version, and status of the file (raw data, processed, redundant, etc.)

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

There are no planned data restriction policies for gathered data, data will be made available openly to anyone who might be interested in said data. An exception may apply if, during this project, any data may be protected because of confidentiality reasons (restricted access information, trade secrets, etc.)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The embargo period may be applied for the period in which in any particular study or experiment information is gathered and data sets are worked up to protect the research. After completion of the study or publication, all relevant data will be made openly available, including Matlab scripts developed for information processing and analysis.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

Currently, it is not planned to use the repository to make data, its associated metadata, and any other documentation accessible. Because of the nature of the study, it is a better approach to add information and access possibilities to each published research article, because the gathered data is strongly connected with performed experiments and could be of little use without proper context.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

During the data acquisition, processing and analysis data may be stored in proprietary data formats, which would require the use of software tools, such as Microsoft Office, Matlab (executable scripts, graphs), OptSim (optical fiber network simulation schemes), OptiGratting (FBG sensor simulation schemes). Once the data is processed for long-term data storage and preservation, the data will be stored in open-access formats to ensure that the data is not lost to possible incompatibility issues and is accessible to anyone without a need for specialized software tools, see below.

Plain text, program executable codes and scripts will be stored as **.txt** files.

Tabular text and spreadsheets will be stored **.csv**, **.tsv** files.

Image files such as graphs will be stored as **.tiff** files.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

As mentioned before all plain text will be stored in .txt format, and tabular data will be stored as either .csv or .tsv. Images and graphs will be stored as .tiff. For these file formats, there are a multitude of freely available open-source software.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

It is an open-source license. This license enables re-users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data mentioned will be made available for reuse in parts adjacent to each of the studies or experiments taking place during this project after the data is gathered, processed and analyzed, to ensure that all data is complete, usable, in its final versions and meets the quality control standards.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data quality assurance:

When possible data will be normalized, to ensure it does not exhibit anomalies and is in a standardized form with a consistent structure and data types. Data will also be rigorously analyzed and screened to reduce the possibility of errors.

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Nauris Silkans (orcid:0009-0004-4683-1026)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

All data will be stored in Microsoft OneDrive cloud which applies many security measures, such as passwords, firewalls and encryption of the data. Most important and relevant data will be backed up in an external storage device residing in the RTU facility.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

